

Journal article - Men in early childhood education in New Zealand.

Focusing on post covid timeline.

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Critical pedagogy is a process of over and over reflecting on one's practice, ideas, and opinions that are shaped by personal experiences, lenses, stereotypes or simply following the 'givens' with "this is how we do things here" mentality. Smith & McLaren, 2010, state that "critical pedagogy challenges the social, environmental, and economic structures and social relations that shape the conditions in which people live, and in which schools operate"(p.332). In my understanding of critical pedagogy and critical theory, I believe that social 'norms' shape the mindset of teachers, shape the mindset of the child they're teaching and the families they're working with, setting a 'given' in the early childhood environment. Men in early childhood environments is a hot topic of discussion due to a wide number of teachers being females as compared to men and women being widely thought to be natural caregivers (data collected by: Bullough Jr, 2015). This is a given that exists in society as we heard when we were children because that's how we strongly assume things are (Bronfenbrenner's ecological model theory can be observed here). There are multiple factors and facts that support this norm throughout history that are also true but also should not stop us from reflecting and critically examining the status of men in ece, what happens and why it happens, and how can we improve our knowledge, and practices around it. Teachers are leaders, in ways that we cannot imagine. They lead by example, they share their knowledge with tamariki and whanau that shapes their views indirectly and directly, and they have a fundamental role in the society that is irreplaceable. Critical pedagogy is essential for educators and teachers for them to recognize their own social position, and their reactions, uncover assumptions that cover the true understanding of how the world works and strive for intellectual humanity (Di Angelo and Sensoy, 2014).

Men in Early childhood?

This is barely seen in real-life experiences where a man is seen working in an early childhood centre. Socially, this is considered a stereotype that men working in ece are not "manly", are not natural caregivers, may exploit children or are simply backed up by sexual exploitation cases by men in history (Owen, 2003). Economically, due to the social position of men and women in society, men have always chased high-paying jobs, ece being moderately paying jobs does not attract males to work in this environment (Drudy, 2008). Together, these factors work together in discouraging society from letting men work in ece and if they do, there are always a presence of stereotypes that result in practices like bullying, keeping an eye on male teachers, underestimating the practices and philosophies of male teachers or simply not believing in giving the power to be the head in teaching to man because he does not understand how children learn better than a woman (Vandenbroeck & Peeters, 2008).

When critically reflecting on our practice, Why is this such a norm for men to be viewed from this perspective in ece? We know that it is a given in society and we also recognize why it is a given but what are we doing to peel off these stereotypical and societal norms and work with equality? How does it support children's learning?

Sumison (2005) concluded, "As far as these children are concerned, a very tentative answer to [the] question, 'Do men offer something different in their work with young children on account of their being men?' Would appear to be no" (p. 120). However continuing with the given norm of men in ece being not appropriate will directly and indirectly, impact tamariki's thinking, learning, and view of the world ("Vygotsky's ideas that learning leads to development and occurs in relationships with people, places and things, mediated by participation in valued social and cultural activities" Ministry Of Education, 2017, p61).

Children are not concerned with who teaches them. We shouldn't be too. Our gender does not define who we are and how we are part of a child's learning. Therefore I believe that these biases, stereotypes and lenses should be cleared and teachers should just be viewed as "humans" and not men or women in practice to eliminate discrimination in this sector, discrimination in a child's learning and development. Children learn from teachers, their thoughts and practices, and it is our responsibility to not plant the seed of discrimination in their early childhood, to not model stereotypes in front of them and to not push them divide gender roles as they see it in front of them.

Policies around men in ece in New Zealand.

Pathways to the Future (Ministry of Education, 2002), the ECE strategic plan, does not directly address the shortfall of male educators, and no government program exists to improve male recruitment. However, the Ministry of Education's Desirable Objectives and Practices (1998) require businesses to develop policies that are inclusive and fair, and that represent the ideals of equal employment opportunities (Jones, 2009).

But why shall I talk about men in ece? How does it serve me?

As an educator who teaches and learns, and critically thinks about my place, my practices, and my impact on society, I need to talk about men in ece. Socially, there are more women in the childcare industry because they are observed as natural caregivers and merely as "babysitters" (Peeters, 2007) by most, which may be related to misogyny, discrimination, and a patriarchal society. I aim at eliminating this belief in my practice, and environment and strongly advocate for women being more than just caretakers. Men in ece provide an opportunity for women to work for a change in the way childcare workers are seen and associated with a particular gender (Adams, Openshaw & Hamer, 2005; Dau, 2001; Peeters, 2007). Not only does it support us in eliminating stereotypes, misogyny, and discrimination in this field but also opens up a door for men to actually connect with their emotional side, learn about Hauora, share their knowledge, lead with equality and take charge of teaching the youth as much as women. It serves me as a woman to live a life socially, economically, mentally, and holistically equal to that of a man. And it serves me as a teacher as I am able to

preach what I believe in equality. Or my philosophy of *Te Whāriki* requires children to 'experience an environment where there are equitable opportunities for learning, irrespective of gender' (Ministry of Education, 1996, p. 66). We include men in a female-dominant work environment, creating inclusive opportunities and modeling these practices to children. They grow up not dividing gender roles, they grow up learning about acceptance, diversity, upholding each other's mana, caring about their own and others' wellbeing, and communicating with the thought of us all being "humans" and not men and women fit to our stereotypes.

Both Ranginui (sky father) and Papatuanuku (mother earth) are our teachers. Nature and the universe don't differentiate among its creations, knowledge, whakapapa, resources and teachings. In Maori world view, papatuanuku is the mother of creation, where we come from and where will eventually go back to (Marsden, 1985). She teaches us about life, our land, our resources, our genealogy, we become who we are because of our interactions with Papatuanuku (Marsden, 1985). Much of life, in the Māori worldview, is about discovering one's tūrangawaewae, one's basis and place in the world. This has typically been conveyed through a people's relationship with certain locations, such as a mountain, a river, or other significant landmarks. She plays an equally important role in our lives as Ranginui (sky father). Ranginui is known to be the early source of knowledge and life.

According to one legend, the god Tane ascended to the castle Te Tihi-o-Manono in the highest of the 12 heavens, Te Toi-o-ng-rangi. He returned with three baskets of knowledge: te kete-tuatea (basket of light), te kete-tuauri (basket of darkness), and te kete-aronui (basket of wisdom) (basket of pursuit). Each basket means something different to different people. According to the scholar Maori Marsden, the basket of light represents present knowledge, the basket of darkness represents the unknown, and the basket of chase represents the information humanity are actively seeking (Rāwiri Taonui, 2006).

Both mother and father teach us, they represent the unique knowledge they possess and the love they share for us. As teachers, we shall draw inspiration from the Maori World view where we share our knowledge with everyone, irrespective of gender. To me, this is the aim of inclusion, including men in ece.

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